

Cycloaddition reactions of 2- or 3-substituted 1-benzopyran-4-ones having a double bond in conjugation with the pyran 2,3-olefinic bond[†]

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Abstract : Different types of cycloaddition reactions involving either the pyran 2,3-olefinic bond or the exocyclic double bond or the diene system contained in the title 1-benzopyran-4-ones are discussed.

Keywords : 4-Oxo-4H-1-benzopyran, cycloaddition, diene, dienophile, dipolarophile.

Introduction

Cycloaddition reactions of some 1-benzopyran-4-ones (trivial name : chromones) belonging to the general system represented by either A or B [X = carbon or a heteroatom, R = H, Me, Ph etc.] are presented herein. For the sake of brevity, 4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran-2-yl moiety in system A is abbreviated as 'Bpy' and 4-oxo-4H-1-benzopyran-3-yl in B as 'Chr'. Alkyl, alkoxy and halogeno substituents in the benzene ring of the chromone moiety remain unaffected in most of the reactions described here for the compounds having no such substituents. The subject matter is presented here in a few sections based on the type of cycloaddition and subsections based on the nature and participative mode of the substrates in the reactions.

I. [2+2]Cycloaddition

Neither chemical nor photochemical [2+1]- nor chemical [2+2]cycloaddition involving the pyran 2,3-olefinic

bond of chromone is known. The cyclobutene 3 initially formed by [2+2]cycloaddition of exocyclic olefinic bond of 2-(2-dimethylaminovinyl)chromone 1 and alkyne 2 (Y = E = CO₂Me; Y = E = COPh; Y = H, E = CO₂Et) yields the xanthone 4 by a sequence of electrocyclic ring opening, electrocyclisation and dimethylamine elimination, the xanthone 4 (Y = H, E = CO₂Et) being always accompanied by the flavone 5 when ethyl propiolate (2, Y = H, E = CO₂Et) is used as the alkyne^{1,2}. The chloroketen 7 (R = H, Cl) adds across the azomethine double bond of 2-(aryliminomethyl)chromone 6 forming the azetidin-2-one 8, the product being a 1 : 1 isomeric mixture³ for R = H.

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II. [3+2]Cycloaddition

II.1. 1,3-Dipolar cycloaddition to the pyran 2,3-olefinic bond

An acyl group at 3-position of chromone **9** makes its 2,3-double bond highly susceptible to a 1,3-dipole. Thus, diazomethane undergoes *cis*-addition to 2,3-double bond of 3-formylchromone **9a** to give the unstable 1-pyrazoline intermediate **10** (R = H) that ultimately leads to 3-acetyl-2-methylchromone **11b**, the furochromone **12a** and the fused pyrazole **13** (Scheme 1). **10** (R = H) gives by a concerted electrocyclic elimination of nitrogen and migration of hydrogen **11a** that gets homologated by diazomethane to **11b** (path *a*); it produces **12a** by a 1,5-sigmatropic rearrangement accompanied by nitrogen extrusion (path *b*) and yields **13** by base catalysed deformylation followed by air oxidation, diazomethane or the intermediate **10** (R = H) itself functioning as the base (path *c*)⁴. 3-Acetylchromone **9b** behaves similarly as 3-formylchromone towards diazomethane to give **11b**, **12b** and **13**⁴.

Scheme 1

3-Benzoylchromone **9c** behaves towards diazomethane a bit differently from its analogues **9a,b**. It forms the 2-methylated product **11c** and pyrazole **13** by a mechanism as shown in Scheme 1 (paths *a* and *c*) but no dihydrofuran

as **12c** (path *b*). The exocyclic carbonyl group of 3-benzoylchromone **9c** competes favourably with its less reactive 2,3-olefinic bond. Thus, the addition of diazomethane initially to the carbonyl group results in the ketone **14** and the oxirane **15**; further reaction of diazomethane with the former (**14**) leads to the furobenzopyran **16** through the intermediacy of **10** (R = CH₂Ph) and **12d**, and that with the latter (**15**) gives the pyranopyrazole **17** (Scheme 2); the stereochemistry around the exocyclic double bond of **16** and that of the ring juncture in **17** remain unestablished⁴.

Scheme 2

The acid **9d** on treatment with diazomethane yields the cyclopropane **20** (stereoisomeric mixture), the furobenzopyran **22**, and the pyrazoles **13** and **23** in complete exclusion of **9e** and its 2-methylhomologue **11d**⁵. The [3+2]cycloadduct **18** of **9d** and diazomethane collapses to the corresponding cyclopropane carboxylic acid **19** (Scheme 3 – path *a*) which is subsequently esterified to **20** by diazomethane. The adduct **18** on decarboxylation and subsequent oxidation gives the pyrazole **13** (path *b*) whereas a formal [1,5]sigmatropic rearrangement of **18** with nitrogen extrusion and acid carbonyl oxygen participation leads to the enol **21** that gets methylated by diazomethane to the furobenzopyran **22** (path *c*). The pyrazole **13** behaves as an azenammine in undergoing 1,4-addition to the α,β-unsaturated ketone functionality of **22** with concomitant elimination of methanol to form the product **23**. Hot methanol converts the cyclopropane **20** to the benzoxepin **24**. Diazomethane converts the ester **9e** to its 2-methyl homologue **11d** and a stereoisomeric mixture of the cyclopropane **20**⁵.

Scheme 3

The formation of the cyclopropane **27** and the xanthone **29** by reaction of 3-formylchromone **9a** with phenyldiazomethane also involves the intermediacy of the [3+2]cycloadduct **25** (Scheme 4)⁶; the cyclopropane **26** generated from **25** reacts further with phenyldiazomethane to give **27** (path *a*) whereas the *C*-benzylated chromone **28** (path *b*) gives with the substrate **9a** the xanthone **29** by a sequence of base catalysed Michael initiated ring closure, water elimination and pyran ring opening.

Scheme 4

The non-isolable [3+2]cycloadduct of **9a**, **d** with pyridinium phenacylide gives ultimately the indolizine **30**⁷. The dipole obtained by interaction of triphenylphosphine with the allenic ester **31** undergoes [3+2]cycloaddition to the pyran 2,3-double bond of **9a** in refluxing benzene, the resultant adduct being deformylated under the reaction conditions to the cyclopentenochromone **32**⁸.

II.2. [3+2]Cycloaddition involving exocyclic olefinic bond

The 1-pyrazoline intermediate arising from [3+2]cycloaddition of diazomethane to the 1,1-diacylethylene **33** gives the 2-pyrazoline **35** by deacetylation and the dihydrofuran **36** by [1,5]sigmatropic rearrangement with participation of acetyl carbonyl and extrusion of nitrogen⁹. The analogous 1-pyrazoline derived from **34** and diazomethane is stable and it does not undergo deacetylation to give **35** (R = OEt), but gives the dihydrofuran **36** (R = OEt) on heating^{10,11}.

Diazomethane brings about *C*-methylation of the acrylic esters **37** and **39** to **38** and **40**, respectively. The diester **38** is inert towards diazomethane whereas **40** reacts further. The 1-pyrazoline **41** thus formed isomerises to 2-pyrazoline **42** (Scheme 5 - path *a*), elides nitrogen to form a stereoisomeric mixture of the cyclopropane **43** (path *b*) and undergoes a formal [1,5]sigmatropic rearrangement involving ester carbonyl oxygen with concomitant nitrogen extrusion to dihydrofuran **44** (path *c*). On heating over its melting point, **44** rearranges to **43**. Rearrangement of an acylcyclopropane to a dihydrofuran is common; so the thermal rearrangement of **44** to **43** is

regarded as a reversed alkoxy-carbonylcyclopropane \rightarrow 5-alkoxy-2,3-dihydrofuran transformation^{10,11}.

Scheme 5

The pyran 2,3-double bond in chromone **45** competes to some extent with its exocyclic olefinic bond in capturing phenyldiazomethane; the resultant cycloadduct gives the 2-benzylated chromone **46** existing in the tautomeric form **47** at least in chloroform solution (Scheme 6 – path A)¹². The 1-pyrazoline intermediate derived by addition of phenyldiazomethane to the exocyclic alkenic bond of **45** (path B) assumes a preferred conformation as shown in **48** with both phenyl and benzopyran-3-yl (R) groups occupying the pseudo equatorial positions. It gives the pyrazole **49** by base catalysed monodeacetylation followed by air oxidation or disproportionation (path Ba), and the *trans*-cyclopropane **50** by nitrogen extrusion (path Bb). In the 1-pyrazoline \rightarrow olefin transformation process, it is the R group (benzopyran moiety) that being *trans* to C–N bond in **48** migrates to C-5 in concert with nitrogen elimination to yield the olefin **51** that further reacts with phenyldiazomethane to give the dihydrofuran **53** through the 1-pyrazoline intermediate **52** (path Bc). The conversion of 4-monosubstituted 5-phenyl-1-pyrazoline **48** to the olefin **51** is the first example of facile migration of a hetaryl group over hydrogen. The cyclopropane **50** thermally rearranges to the dihydrofuran **54**.

III. [4+2]Cycloaddition

[4+2]Cycloaddition, also named as Diels-Alder (D-A) reaction, is of two types. Cycloaddition involving an electron rich diene (or heterodiene) and an electron deficient dienophile (alkene or alkyne) is called the normal

Scheme 6

(or hetero) D-A reaction whereas that between an electron deficient diene (or heterodiene) and an electron rich olefin is termed as Inverse Electron Demand Diels-Alder (IEDDA) reaction. Both types of cycloaddition are known for the title chromone systems.

III.1. 2,3-Olefinic bond of 3-acylchromone as a 2 π component

[4+2]Cycloaddition of 2,3-dimethylbuta-1,3-diene with the chromones **9a** and 3-ethoxycarbonylchromone necessitates the use of catalytic amount of titanium tetrachloride, the former chromone giving the deformylated adduct **55a** and the latter **55b**¹³. The addition of highly electron rich diene as **56** (Y = OTMS, OTBS) with the said chromone derivatives does not need any Lewis acid catalyst to form a mixture of **57** (X = CHO, CO₂Et), the *endo*-adduct predominating over the *exo*-adduct¹³. The dienamine **1** undergoes D-A reaction with the aldehyde **9a** in refluxing DMF; the adduct ultimately gives 2-salicyloylxanthone by base catalysed elimination of dimethylamine and deformylative pyran ring opening².

D-A reactions of the aldehyde **9a** with several *o*-benzoquinodimethanes¹⁴ and one indole-*o*-quinodimethane¹⁵ have already been comprehended¹⁶.

III.2. 2-Vinylchromone (System A, X = carbon) as a 4 π component

Several 2-(2-aryl- and hetaryl-vinyl)chromones undergo normal D-A reaction (*endo*-addition) with various dienophiles and IEDDA (*exo*-addition) with 1-pyrrolidinylenes and both types of addition are followed by a 1,3-hydrogen shift so as to form the resonance stabilized chromone system; this aspect has been elsewhere comprehended by the present author^{16,17}. Cycloaddition of 2-vinylchromone **1** with *N*-phenylmaleimide (NPMI) is followed by elimination of dimethylamine and air oxidation². It is noteworthy that exocyclic olefinic bond of 2-(2-arylvinyl)-5-hydroxychromone **58** behaves as a 2 π component in its cycloaddition with *o*-benzoquinodimethane to give the adduct **59** that can be aromatized by DDQ to the flavone **60** (Het = 5-hydroxy-4-oxo-4*H*-1-benzopyran-2-yl)¹⁸.

Het = 5-hydroxy-4-oxo-4*H*-1-benzopyran-2-yl

III.3. [4+2]Cycloaddition of the system B

[4+2]Cycloaddition reactions of the chromone based system **B** covering the literature till 2006 have been compiled in an article published from our laboratory¹⁹. Mainly the later publications on the subject with passing references to the earlier ones are mentioned here.

III.3.1. All carbon D-A reaction

Cycloadditions of *Z*- and *E*-isomers of 3-(2-aryl- or hetaryl-vinyl)chromone with *N*-methylmaleimide are stereoselective, the former giving the *endo*-adduct **61a** and the latter *exo*-adduct **61b** (R = Me). In its cycloaddition with comparatively less reactive *N*-phenylmaleimide, the said *Z*-isomer is converted to the *E*-isomer that subsequently undergoes normal D-A reaction with the dienophile giving the *exo*-adduct **61b** (R = Ph)²⁰. D-A reactions of several 3-(2-hetaryl-vinyl)chromones with maleic anhydride in toluene have also been described²¹.

III.3.2. All carbon IEDDA reaction

The formation of 2-hydroxybenzophenone **64** from the electron deficient diene **62** (EWG = CO₂Et) and several acyclic as well as cyclic enamine **63** [X = H, Y = Ph; X = Ph, Y = H; XY = CH₂(CH₂)₁₋₄CH₂ etc.] involves a domino IEDDA, elimination and intramolecular elimination²². Ethoxyethene behaves differently from the enamines in its cycloaddition with the said diene **62**; the initially formed IEDDA adduct eliminates ethanol and the resultant electron deficient cyclodiene **65** captures a second molecule of ethyl vinyl ether to give a stereoisomeric mixture of the tetracycle **66**, no or a little benzophenone **64** (X = Y = H) being formed²³. The yield and *endo* : *exo* ratio of the adduct in this domino IEDDA-elimination-IEDDA reaction sequence is highly solvent dependent. The presence of a hydroxyl group at C-5 of the chromone moiety increases the activity of the diene towards the dienophile. In non-polar solvents the chromone **62** (EWG = CN) with ethoxyethene gives a mixture of cyclic compounds **67** and **68**, the latter arising through an alternative domino IEDDA-elimination-ene reaction sequence and its stereochemistry remaining unsettled²³. IEDDA of the vinylchromone **62** (EWG = COMe, COPh, CO₂Et, CONEt₂, SO₂Ph, CN, aryl) with the electron rich ethene **69** (R = R¹ = OMe; R = H, R¹ = NMe₂) is followed by elimination so as to produce the xanthone **70**²⁴.

III.3.3. Heterodiene in normal D-A reaction

The hydrazone **71** of the aldehyde **9a** is a sufficiently electron rich heterodiene so as to form with NPMI the cycloadduct **75** that can be aromatized by Pd-C to the azaxanthone **76** whereas the anil **72** (indeed an electron deficient heterodiene – *vide infra*) fails to react²⁵. The azadienes **73** and **74** behave differently from their respective lower homologues **71** and **72** towards NPMI. The hydrazone **73** participates through its enehydrazine tautomer (*o*-quinodimethane) **77** ($R^1 = NMe_2$) in the normal D-A reaction with NPMI giving the *endo*-adduct **78**; NPMI brings about to some extent elimination of dimethylamine from **73** so as to form 3-cyano-2-methylchromone. The anil **74**, like the analogous hydrazone **73**, gives through its tautomer **77** ($R^1 = C_6H_4Me-p$) the adduct **79**. Palladised charcoal converts **78** and **79** to the respective fully aromatized xanthenes **80** and **81**²⁵.

The cycloaddition of 3-formylchromone with the alkyne **2** ($Y = H, Ph, CO_2Me, CO_2Et$; $E = CO_2Me, CO_2Et$) in the presence of triphenylphosphine or DABCO²⁶ or 4-picoline²⁷ to form the adduct **82** is not a D-A reaction in true sense; it is better termed as an organocatalytic hetero D-A type reaction. The *S*-isomer of the fused pyran **82** ($Y = E = CO_2Me$) is formed in nearly 54% ee when **9a** is annulated with DMAD in the presence of a chiral catalyst as β -isoquinidine²⁶.

III.3.4. Heterodiene in IEDDA reaction

IEDDA reaction of 3-acylchromones **9a,d** with diphenylketen²⁸ and domino IEDDA-IEDDA of 3-formylchromone **9a** with dichloroketen²⁹ are known. Cycloadditions of chromones **9a,b,d** with alkoxyolefin $CH_2=CR^1(OR^2)$ ($R^1 = H, Me$; $R^2 = \text{alkyl}$) and some cyclic ethers are discussed in details in two publications^{16,19}. *Endo*-isomer predominates over exo-isomer in the adducts resulting from the addition of 3-(polyfluoroacyl)chromone **9** ($R = CF_3, CF_2H, CF_2CF_2H$) with ethyl vinyl ether, 2,3-dihydrofuran and 3,4-dihydro-2H-pyran³⁰.

The anil **72** functions as an electron deficient diene to undergo [4+2]cycloaddition with chloroketen and phenylchloroketen³ whereas it behaves differently towards 1-vinylpyrrolidin-2-one in water or water-acetonitrile in the presence of ceric ammonium nitrate (CAN); here the azomethine π bond in conjugation with the phenyl π bond undergoes [4+2]cycloaddition with the said pyrrolidine to give the tetrahydroquinoline **83** that can be dehydrogenated by CAN in MeOH at 0°C to **84**³¹.

IV. [4+3]Cycloaddition

The nitrilimine **85** ($R = Me, OEt$; $Ar = p$ -bromophenyl) undergoes [4+3]cycloaddition with the 4 π

component of the anil **72**, apart from [3+2]cycloaddition with its azomethine function, to give the fused triazepin **86**³². Similar annulation of the dipole, derived from the allenic ester **31** and triphenylphosphine, with **72** gives **87** that reorganizes to the azepin **88** (Ar = *p*-tolyl) through a sequence of pyran ring opening, recyclisation and 1,5-hydrogen shift⁸.

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